

NAVIGATING THE WRITING MAZE: AN EXPLORATION OF TECHNICAL – VOCATIONAL- LIVELIHOOD STUDENTS’ WRITING PROFICIENCY

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Navigating the Writing Maze: An Exploration of Technical -Vocational- Livelihood Students' Writing Proficiency

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Abstract

Senior High School students struggle with writing proficiency, which affects their academic performance and future career opportunities. This study examined the writing proficiency of Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) Senior High School students, focusing on content, organization, vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics. It also explored students' experiences in enhancing writing skills and identified effective instructional materials to support writing improvement. Using a Sequential Explanatory Mixed Methods design, the study involved 240 students for quantitative assessment, 16 for in-depth interviews, and two focus group discussions (FGDs). Writing proficiency was assessed through an essay task evaluated with rubrics, while structured interviews and FGDs provided qualitative insights. Descriptive statistics analyzed the quantitative data, and thematic analysis was used for the qualitative findings. Results indicated that students scored below the passing threshold in all areas, averaging a "Failed" status across content, organization, vocabulary, grammar and mechanics, highlighting significant challenges in idea development and grammatical accuracy. Qualitative analysis revealed themes such as writing challenges, support and feedback, grammar and language struggles, writing practice, obstacles and distractions, strategies, and collaboration. Both data sets underscored the need for targeted pedagogical strategies. Scaffolded instruction and redesigned curricula, including workshops and structured activities, were recommended to address these foundational areas and improve students' writing skills effectively.

Keywords: *writing proficiency, Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) students, Mixed methods, academic writing challenges, educational interventions*

Introduction

Writing is a vital macro skill essential for effective communication, enabling individuals to articulate ideas, emotions, and thoughts clearly and logically. However, many learners struggle with mastering writing, as it requires a combination of critical thinking, vocabulary, grammar, and organization (Mabolo & Millendez, 2020). These challenges often hinder students' academic performance and their ability to express themselves effectively, creating a pressing need for interventions to improve writing proficiency (Adrias, 2022; Wang, 2020).

Globally, writing proficiency remains a significant concern, with data from the National Assessment of Educational Progress (2019) and Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority (2017) indicating that less than half of high school students achieve proficiency in writing, and average scores have declined over time. In Albania, high school students face similar struggles, particularly in writing in English, highlighting the universal nature of this issue (Sogutlu & Veliaj-Ostrosi, 2022). These findings underscore the importance of addressing writing challenges to enhance students' communication skills worldwide.

In the Philippines, writing proficiency is similarly problematic, as less than half of Grade 6 and Grade 10 students demonstrate coherent writing skills due to limited exposure to English, insufficient vocabulary, and inadequate practice (Garnera et al., 2019). Filipino high school students also grapple with grammar, sentence construction, coherence, and critical thinking in writing, limiting their ability to generate ideas and arguments effectively (Mabolo & Millendez, 2020; Talala & Delos Santos, 2018). National programs like the Early Language Literacy and Numeracy Program (ELLNP) and the K to 12 curriculum aim to address these issues, but significant gaps persist.

At a high school in Sultan Kudarat Province, the challenges are even more pronounced among Technical Vocational and Livelihood (TVL) students. Unlike their peers in the Academic track, TVL students face unique difficulties due to diverse literacy levels and a one-size-fits-all instructional approach (de Jong et al., 2018). Data from the School Monitoring Enhancement Plan and Assessment (2022) and Learning Action Cell sessions (2023) reveal that writing-related skills are consistently the least mastered competencies among TVL students. This lack of proficiency impedes their ability to express ideas effectively, contributing to lower English proficiency ratings compared to students in other strands (Ella, 2018).

Despite the global, national, and local efforts to improve writing proficiency, there is limited research focusing on the specific challenges faced by TVL students in the Philippines, particularly in Sultan Kudarat. Existing studies often prioritize students in academically oriented strands, leaving a gap in understanding the unique struggles and experiences of TVL learners. Addressing this gap, the current study seeks to determine TVL students' writing proficiency, explore the factors contributing to their difficulties, and establish a foundation for targeted interventions to enhance their writing skills and meet their diverse needs.

This study theoretical framework integrates four key theories—Cognitive Load Theory, Schema Theory, the Simple View of Writing,

and Rhetorical Structure Theory—to address writing proficiency among TVL senior high school students. Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988) emphasizes reducing cognitive demands to enhance learning and retention, particularly in writing mechanics such as punctuation and grammar. Schema Theory (Kant, 1998; Rumelhart, 1980), supported by Neisser’s Perceptual Cycle Model (Neisser, 1976), highlights the role of existing knowledge structures in shaping comprehension and content creation, with top-down and bottom-up learning approaches aiding in processing and organizing information. The Simple View of Writing (Berninger et al., 2002) explains writing as a combination of text generation, transcription, and executive functions, emphasizing how deficiencies in lower-level skills like spelling and grammar can impact overall composition quality.

Together, these theories offer a cognitive basis for enhancing writing proficiency by addressing key challenges in mechanics, content, and coherence. Their integration into this study provides a structured approach to understanding students' writing difficulties and developing targeted interventions. Cognitive Load Theory supports the design of instructional strategies that minimize cognitive overload, allowing students to focus on mastering writing fundamentals. Schema Theory informs the development of scaffolding techniques that build on students' prior knowledge to improve comprehension and content organization. The Simple View of Writing underscores the necessity of balancing transcription skills with higher order writing processes, guiding pedagogical approaches that strengthen both foundational and complex writing abilities. By applying these theories, the study aims to identify effective teaching strategies that foster writing development and improve overall proficiency among TVL students.

Complementing these, Rhetorical Structure Theory (Mann & Thompson, 1987) provides a framework for understanding and improving the organization of text, emphasizing the role of rhetorical relationships in producing cohesive and coherent writing. These theories collectively underpin the study holistic approach to writing instruction, targeting critical components such as grammar, organization, and content while addressing cognitive demands. By applying this framework, the study aims to enhance the writing proficiency of TVL students, emphasizing evidence-based strategies to develop their skills and bridge gaps identified in academic and professional writing contexts.

The study aimed to determine the writing proficiency of the TVL Senior high school students. Specifically, it aims to investigate the proficiency level of TVL senior high school students considering content, organization, vocabulary, grammar and language use, and mechanics. The study also explored how the TVL Senior High School students describe their experiences in improving writing proficiency in their academic writing subjects and how their writing proficiency levels align with their experiences. In addition, based on the findings, what instructional materials may be developed to enhance the writing proficiency of TVL students.

This study used a mixed-methods design to assess the writing proficiency of Grade 11 TVL students in Sultan Kudarat Province and explore their academic writing experiences. Quantitative data was collected through a writing test using a rating scale for content, organization, vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics, while qualitative data came from interviews and focus groups, providing insights into students' experiences. The study targeted sub-strands like Electrical Installation and Maintenance (EIM), Information Communication and Technology (ICT), Home Economics (HE), and Automotive. Purposeful sampling was conducted at the largest high school, chosen for its diverse population and academic and vocational offerings.

Literature Review

Writing proficiency is a comprehensive skill that serves critical academic and professional purposes, encompassing effective communication, persuasion, and the expression of ideas. It requires the integration of various elements, including content, organization, vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics, which collectively contribute to the quality of writing (Rohim, 2019). Proficient writing demonstrates fluent expression, clarity, logical sequencing, and cohesion. However, traditional teaching methods emphasizing isolated grammar and vocabulary instruction often hinder these abilities. Instead, innovative strategies such as collaborative writing, creative exercises, and feedback loops have proven effective in fostering students' ability to write fluently and coherently (Behera, 2023; Cheng & Zhang, 2021). A holistic approach that integrates these elements with targeted feedback and technological support is essential for improving writing outcomes.

Content forms the foundation of writing, representing the substance and main ideas conveyed by the writer. High-quality content is characterized by relevance, logical development, and coherence in addressing the topic (Wahyudin, 2018; Rohim, 2019). Studies emphasize that well-developed content should effectively tackle the issue under discussion while transitioning seamlessly between ideas to maintain clarity and emphasis (Azhar, 2013; Aytenfsu, 2017). Frameworks for evaluating writing proficiency, such as those proposed by Haswell (2005) and cited in Brooks (2013), highlight knowledge of the topic, substantiveness, and relevance as critical components of content quality. This underscores the need for instructional strategies that foster critical thinking, effective idea generation, and content development in student writing.

Organization is integral to effective communication in writing, ensuring that ideas are presented logically and coherently. It involves structuring content into clear sections such as the introduction, body, and conclusion, while maintaining logical flow within paragraphs and across sentences (Purba & Sihombing, 2020). Effective organization enhances the reader's understanding and engagement, making the text distinct, focused, and persuasive (Musharraf et al., 2020; Rashid & Islam, 2021). Key criteria such as logical sequencing, fluent expression, and cohesion are essential for assessing writing organization (Brooks, 2013). Strategies like cognitive scaffolding, thematic progression, and collaborative tasks have been shown to improve students' ability to organize their ideas effectively (Olson et al., 2023;

Darmila et al., 2020).

Vocabulary is a cornerstone of writing proficiency, enabling precise and nuanced communication. Advanced vocabulary enhances clarity and coherence while allowing writers to tailor their language to various contexts and audiences (Moon et al., 2019; Isma, 2023). Proficient vocabulary use includes sophisticated word choices, idiomatic expressions, collocations, and adherence to an appropriate register. Instructional strategies such as explicit teaching, collaborative learning, extensive reading, and the integration of tools like online writing assistants support vocabulary acquisition and effective application in writing (Puspitasari, 2024; Grami, 2020). These approaches equip students with the lexical knowledge and skills needed to produce refined, contextually appropriate compositions.

Grammar and language use are essential for clarity, precision, and effective communication in writing. Mastery of complex sentence constructions, grammatical accuracy, and the use of appropriate voice and tone enhances the overall quality of written texts (Jung et al., 2019; Villaruz, 2024). Correctness in grammar, achieved through explicit and structured instruction, is particularly critical for EFL learners navigating the complexities of second-language writing (Hakimi, 2021; Benitez-Correa et al., 2019). The strategic use of language devices, supported by technology and collaborative practices, further develops expressiveness and coherence in writing (Mart, 2021; Aguion et al., 2021). A comprehensive approach integrating cognitive strategies, motivation, and reflective practices is essential to address the challenges students face in mastering grammar and language use.

Mechanics refers to the technical aspects of writing, including spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and paragraphing, which are fundamental for ensuring clarity and professionalism in written communication (Rohim, 2019; Purnamasari et al., 2021). Spelling impacts readability and credibility, while punctuation clarifies meaning and flow within texts (Mustadi & Amalia, 2020; Göçen, 2019). Capitalization enhances coherence and professional presentation, and paragraphing organizes ideas into a logical and engaging structure (Kahraman & Kaya, 2024; Ramadhanti & Yanda, 2021). Instructional strategies such as explicit teaching, peer feedback, and the integration of technology have proven effective in improving these skills, emphasizing the importance of mechanics in writing education. These approaches ensure adherence to academic conventions and foster the development of proficient, polished writing.

Writing proficiency of TVL Students

In a landmark move in 2011, the Department of Education introduced the Kinder to 12 Program (K-12), which marked a significant shift from the traditional 10-year basic education curriculum. This change aimed to equip learners with the necessary knowledge and skills to succeed in their chosen paths, be it in higher education, employment, or entrepreneurship. Senior High School (SHS) is the final two years of the K-12 program, comprising Grade 11 and Grade 12. The addition of these two years aims to provide learners with a more comprehensive and holistic education that prepares them for the challenges of the 21st century.

In addition, the Senior High School offers four tracks, each tailored to meet the specific needs and aspirations of learners. The Academic Track provides a solid foundation for higher education, while the Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) Track equips learners with job-ready skills. The Sports Track is designed for those interested in physical education and recreation, while the Arts and Design Track is purpose-built for those seeking to enter creative and performative industries. The Senior High School program empowers learners to choose a path that best suits their interests and skills by offering these tracks. This program's introduction has been a critical milestone in the Philippines' education system, providing learners with the tools they need to succeed in today's dynamic and ever-changing world.

The relationship between the findings of comparative studies and the descriptive correlational study of Domantay and Ramos (2018) reveals that students in different strands of education exhibit varying levels of language proficiency. STEM students tend to perform well in written language proficiency tests, while those in HESS/HUMSS, TVL, and GAS strands tend to perform below average (Macado & Diano, 2021). Specifically, the study by Domantay and Ramos (2018) focused on TVL students and found that most of the respondents needed higher performance in writing competency. These findings underscore the importance of addressing the language proficiency of students in all strands of education, particularly those in the TVL and HESS/HUMSS strands. Improving language proficiency is crucial for students to succeed in their future careers, whether it be in higher education, employment, or entrepreneurship. In this regard, teachers play a pivotal role in motivating students to learn and enhancing their communication and writing skills (Herida & Enriquez, 2020). Thus, concerted efforts are needed to improve the language proficiency of students across all strands, and targeted interventions should be developed to help students enhance their writing skills, considering the performance gap observed across age groups, as highlighted by Domantay and Ramos (2018).

The Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) Strand is a curriculum that combines Required Courses and hands-on courses to help prepare students for TESDA National Certification Assessments. However, studies have shown that TVL students have lower mean English proficiency scores compared to students from other strands in the Senior High School (SHS) program. A descriptive quantitative study conducted by Ella (2018) found that TVL students had the lowest mean English proficiency score compared to other strands. The study also found that metacognitive strategies were the most commonly used learning strategy among SHS students, with no significant correlation between learning strategies and English proficiency. The study proposed that a standardized exam of language skills should be used to measure senior high school students' English competency accurately.

Moreover, metacognitive strategies have been highlighted as critical in addressing the challenges faced by TVL students. A significant body of research emphasizes the importance of metacognitive strategies in improving writing skills. Çer (2019) posits that

metacognitive awareness plays a crucial role in enhancing writing proficiency, suggesting that students who engage in metacognitive strategies are better equipped to plan, monitor, and evaluate their writing processes. This assertion is supported by Villaruz (2024), who found that metacognitive awareness correlates with improved academic writing skills, indicating that students who are conscious of their writing strategies tend to perform better academically. Such findings underscore the necessity of incorporating metacognitive training into the curriculum for TVL students, as it can lead to significant improvements in their writing abilities.

The challenges faced by vocational students in developing their English writing skills are well documented. Siregar et al. (2022) highlight that many vocational students struggle with writing, despite its importance in meeting industry standards. This struggle is compounded by the fact that writing is often perceived as a daunting task, leading to anxiety and decreased motivation among students (Chang, 2024). The need for targeted interventions that address these challenges is critical. For instance, the use of collaborative writing techniques has been shown to enhance students' confidence and writing skills, as evidenced by Yundayani et al. (2020), who reported that collaborative writing activities significantly improved students' self-efficacy in writing. Such collaborative approaches can foster a supportive learning environment, encouraging students to share ideas and provide feedback to one another.

The integration of technology in writing instruction has also emerged as a promising avenue for enhancing writing proficiency among TVL students. Azir (2022) discusses the potential of virtual reality (VR) in engaging students and improving their writing skills, although the immediate benefits may not be as pronounced as anticipated. This highlights the complexity of using technology in educational settings, where the effectiveness of such tools can vary based on implementation and student engagement. Furthermore, interactive video resources have been identified as effective in addressing the unique needs of vocational students, as noted by Darmayanti (2023), who emphasizes the importance of tailoring instructional methods to enhance language proficiency and professional readiness. These technological innovations can provide dynamic and relevant contexts for writing practice, making the learning experience more engaging for students.

In addition, the role of peer feedback in writing development must be considered. Wu and Schunn (2020) found that providing and receiving peer feedback significantly enhances writing performance among students, as it encourages critical reflection and collaborative learning. This aligns with the findings of Yang (2023), who emphasizes the importance of writing strategies in fostering proficiency among vocational college students. Thereby improving their writing skills in a supportive environment by incorporating structured peer feedback sessions into writing curricula, educators can create opportunities for students to learn from one another.

Writing proficiency is also closely linked to students' motivation and engagement in the writing process. Chang (2024) highlights that asynchronous cross-cultural communication can enhance writing performance and motivation among students, particularly those with lower proficiency levels. This suggests that fostering a sense of community and connection among students can lead to improved writing outcomes. Similarly, the Motivation-Strategy-Proficiency-based Writing Enhancement Program proposed by Zhang (2023) aims to holistically improve academic writing skills by addressing the interplay between motivation, strategy use, and proficiency. Such comprehensive programs are essential for equipping TVL students with the necessary skills to succeed in their future careers.

To address the specific contexts and challenges faced by TVL students, the need for targeted writing instruction is paramount. As highlighted by Listiyanto et al. (2020), understanding the factors that contribute to writing strategy choices among students can inform instructional practices and lead to better writing outcomes. Additionally, Ratnaningsih and Azizah (2019) underscore the importance of identifying common mistakes to tailor teaching strategies effectively. Educators can develop more effective writing curricula that address the unique challenges faced by TVL students by focusing on the specific needs of students.

Methodology

This study employed a sequential explanatory mixed-methods research design (Creswell & Creswell, 2017), integrating quantitative and qualitative data to explore the writing proficiency of Technical-Vocational-Livelihood (TVL) Senior High School students. The design, denoted as "QUAN → qual," prioritized quantitative analysis, followed by qualitative data collection to explain and expand upon the initial findings. The quantitative phase utilized descriptive statistics to assess writing proficiency, while the qualitative phase delved into students' experiences through in-depth interviews (IDI) and focus group discussions (FGD), fostering a comprehensive understanding of their writing journeys. This approach enabled the exploration of the underlying factors affecting TVL students' writing proficiency and provided insights for tailored instructional interventions.

The study involved 738 Grade 11 TVL students from Sultan Kudarat Province, representing four sub-strands: Electrical Installation and Maintenance (EIM), Information Communication Technology (ICT), Home Economics (HE), and Automotive. Random sampling was employed for the quantitative phase, yielding a sample size of 267 students based on Slovin's formula. For the qualitative phase, 16 students (4 per strand) were purposefully selected for IDI, and two FGDs comprising 10 students each were conducted. This sampling ensured representation across gender, sub-strands, and varying English proficiency levels while achieving thematic saturation.

Key instruments included an essay writing task, an essay writing rubric, and validated guides for IDI and FGD. The essay writing task required participants to write structured narratives about their research writing journeys, aligned with the Senior High School curriculum guide. This provided insights into content, vocabulary, mechanics, grammar, and organization. The essay writing rubric, adapted from Haswell's ESL Composition Profile (Brooks, 2013), assessed five criteria—content, organization, vocabulary, grammar,

and mechanics—on a scale ranging from “very poor” to “excellent.” The IDI and FGD guides, validated by language experts, elicited detailed insights into students’ experiences, challenges, and strategies in writing.

Data collection followed a structured, sequential process. The quantitative phase involved administering essay writing tasks in a controlled environment, ensuring fairness and preventing academic dishonesty. Essays were evaluated by three independent raters, with inter-rater reliability assessed using Krippendorff’s alpha. In the qualitative phase, participants for IDI and FGD were selected based on quantitative results. Interviews and discussions were conducted in a supportive environment, encouraging openness and candid responses. Data collection continued until thematic saturation was achieved.

Quantitative data analysis involved evaluating writing proficiency using a 5-point rating scale for each criterion, with scores converted to grades based on the DepEd grading system. Individual components such as content and mechanics were assessed, with indicators tallied to derive overall scores. Qualitative data analysis employed thematic analysis, involving coding, categorization, and theme development. This systematic process identified recurring patterns and themes, providing deeper insights into students’ writing experiences. Findings from both phases were integrated using joint displays, which visually highlighted the alignment and complementarity of quantitative and qualitative data.

Ethical principles guided every aspect of the research. Participants and parents (for minors) provided voluntary informed consent, ensuring their autonomy and understanding of the study. Confidentiality was maintained through data anonymization and secure storage protocols. Students had the right to withdraw at any stage without repercussions, ensuring voluntary participation. Findings were disseminated transparently to stakeholders, emphasizing collective insights while safeguarding individual data.

The study adhered to established qualitative research standards to ensure credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. Member checking allowed participants to validate IDI and FGD transcripts, while expert validation of procedures and thematic analyses enhanced reliability. Detailed procedures and a transparent methodology ensured the findings’ applicability to similar contexts. This rigorous and systematic approach provided robust insights into the writing proficiency of TVL students, contributing valuable knowledge for improving writing instruction in vocational education contexts.

Results and Discussion

In this section, the results of the study are presented, analyzed, and interpreted to create a meaningful outcome. The organization of the chapter follows the problems in the research questions, (1) the results of the writing proficiency level of TVL senior high school students considering the content, organization, vocabulary, grammar and language use, and mechanics, (2) the experiences of TVL senior high school students in improving writing proficiency in their academic writing subjects, and (3) alignment of the results of the writing proficiency levels of TVL senior high school students with their experiences.

Proficiency level of TVL Senior High School Students considering the Content, Organization, Vocabulary, Grammar and language use, and Mechanics

This section presents the QUAN findings, specifically the ratings obtained by the TVL Senior high school students on their writing proficiency. Using descriptive statistics, the evaluation results of the students’ written essays are organized in tabular form, based on credible raters strictly following the evaluation rating scale. In addition, it presents the findings, analyzes the data with the observational input from the raters, and synthesizes them with the literature.

Table 1 shows the writing proficiency of the TVL students across five aspects: Content, Organization, Vocabulary, Grammar and Language Use, and Mechanics. Two specifics are examined for each aspect, including mean scores and rating descriptions, which provide a closer look at student performance. It also includes a transmuted grade for each of the main categories along with a transmuted grade descriptor.

Table 1. Summary of Writing Proficiency of the TVL students in terms of Content, Organization, Vocabulary, Grammar and Language Use, and Mechanics

Aspect of Writing Proficiency	Criteria	Rating (Mean Score)	Rating Description	Transmuted Grade	Transmuted Grade Description
Content	Knowledge of the Topic	1.83	Poor	69	Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed
	Substantiveness	1.7	Poor		
	Thorough Development of Thesis	1.6	Poor		
	Relevance to the Assigned Topic	2.11	Poor		
Organization	Fluent Expression/Ideas Clearly Stated	1.61	Poor	68	Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed
	Succinctness	1.67	Poor		
	Logical Sequencing	1.62	Poor		
	Cohesion	1.62	Poor		
Vocabulary	Sophisticated Range	1.45	Very Poor	67	Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed
	Effective Word/Idiom Choice and	1.5	Poor		

		Usage			
Grammar and Language Use	Word Form Mastery	1.53	Poor	67	Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed
	Appropriate Register	1.74	Poor		
	Effective Complex Constructions	1.44	Very Poor		
	Correctness and Accuracy	1.49	Very Poor		
	Appropriate Voice and Tone	1.81	Poor		
Mechanics	Effective Use of Language Devices	1.46	Very Poor	67	Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed
	Spelling	1.56	Poor		
	Punctuation	1.52	Poor		
	Capitalization	1.57	Poor		
	Paragraphing	1.59	Poor		
		Overall Writing Proficiency	67.6	Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed	

The outcomes show that, on average, the students “Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed” in all areas of writing proficiency. For example, the overall rating of writing proficiency in terms of content was 7.25 out of 20, resulting in a transmuted grade of 69, categorized as “Did Not Meet Expectations/Failed.” Individual indicators—Knowledge of the Topic (1.83), Substantiveness (1.70), Thorough Development of Thesis (1.60), and Relevance to the Assigned Topic (2.11)—were rated as “Poor,” reflecting students’ struggles with content development.

These results align with Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988), which suggests that the cognitive demands of integrating ideas, constructing arguments, and organizing content can overwhelm students, inhibiting their ability to produce substantive writing (Dissaux & Jancart, 2022). The findings are consistent with research by Haswell (2005), as cited in Brooks (2013), emphasizing that limited knowledge of the topic impairs content development. Macías and Dack (2023) similarly highlight challenges in achieving depth and reflectiveness, essential for substantive and thesis-driven writing. The relatively higher score for “Relevance to the Assigned Topic” (2.11) indicates students’ general ability to address the theme, though limited in depth and exploration. Qin (2023) underscores that relevance is foundational but insufficient without substantive expansion and critical engagement. These findings suggest a need for scaffolding and guided writing strategies to improve content proficiency.

In terms of organization, the overall rating was 6.51 out of 20, with a transmuted grade of 68, categorized as “Did Not Meet Expectations/Failed.” Indicators such as Fluent Expression/Ideas Clearly Stated (1.61), Succinctness (1.67), Logical Sequencing (1.62), and Cohesion (1.62) were all rated “Poor.”

Schema Theory (Rumelhart, 1980) provides insight into these deficiencies, suggesting that underdeveloped knowledge structures impede students’ ability to sequence ideas logically and maintain cohesion (Hakimzadeh et al., 2021). Olson et al. (2023) highlight that transitioning from “knowledge-telling” to “knowledge-transformation” requires logical organization, a skill underdeveloped in these students. The low scores for Fluent Expression and Succinctness reflect difficulties in articulating ideas concisely and effectively, as noted by Behera (2023). Challenges in Logical Sequencing and Cohesion further emphasize the need for explicit instruction in structuring ideas, supported by research from Tuan (2023), who notes EFL learners’ struggles with cohesive devices. These results suggest targeted interventions focusing on cognitive strategies and structured writing practice.

Moreover, vocabulary proficiency received a mean score of 6.22 out of 20, with a transmuted grade of 67, categorized as “Did Not Meet Expectations/Failed.” Sophisticated Range (1.45) was rated “Very Poor,” while Effective Word/Idiom Choice (1.50), Word Form Mastery (1.53), and Appropriate Register (1.74) were rated as “Poor.” The low scores reflect limited lexical knowledge, which inhibits clarity and precision in communication.

Moon et al. (2019) emphasize the strong correlation between vocabulary range and writing performance, while Rahman (2021) highlights the need for explicit instruction to build a sophisticated vocabulary. The very poor rating for Sophisticated Range suggests inadequate exposure to advanced vocabulary, consistent with Isma (2023), who highlights EFL learners’ challenges in mastering complex words and idiomatic expressions. Difficulties in Word Form Mastery and Appropriate Register further reflect gaps in vocabulary application, as noted by Puspitasari (2024) and Nazzal et al. (2023), underscoring the importance of integrating vocabulary instruction into writing curricula.

Grammar and language use received a mean score of 6.20 out of 20, with a transmuted grade of 67, categorized as “Did Not Meet Expectations/Failed.” Indicators such as Effective Complex Constructions (1.44), Correctness and Accuracy (1.49), and Effective Use of Language Devices (1.46) were rated “Very Poor,” while Appropriate Voice and Tone (1.81) was rated “Poor.” These findings highlight students’ limited ability to construct grammatically sound and contextually appropriate writing.

Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988) suggests that the cognitive demands of balancing grammar with other aspects of writing may contribute to these deficiencies (Paas et al., 2003). The very poor rating for Effective Complex Constructions aligns with Jung et al. (2019), who emphasize the importance of syntactic complexity for writing proficiency. Similarly, Mart (2021) highlights the critical role of grammar accuracy in producing clear and precise writing. Challenges with voice, tone, and language devices underscore the

need for explicit instruction in rhetorical and linguistic strategies to enhance expressiveness and coherence.

Mechanics received a mean score of 6.24 out of 20, with a transmuted grade of 67, categorized as "Did Not Meet Expectations/Failed." Indicators such as Spelling (1.56), Punctuation (1.52), Capitalization (1.57), and Paragraphing (1.59) were all rated "Poor." These findings suggest that students lack mastery of basic writing conventions.

Schema Theory (Anderson & Pearson, 1984) posits that underdeveloped schemas for mechanics hinder the application of these foundational skills. Poor spelling scores align with Mustadi and Amalia (2020), who highlight the role of phonological awareness in spelling proficiency. Errors in punctuation and capitalization, noted by Azizah (2024) and Borong (2023), reflect insufficient practice and understanding of writing conventions. Low paragraphing scores further indicate challenges in organizing ideas coherently, as Kahraman and Kaya (2024) emphasize the importance of structured paragraphing for effective communication.

The Experiences of TVL Senior High School Students in Improving Writing Proficiency in their Academic Writing Subjects

The qualitative phase presents various themes to describe the experiences of TVL senior high school students as they work to enhance their writing skills. The analysis classifies themes into multiple categories: (1) facing writing challenges; (2) receiving support and feedback; (3) engaging in writing practice; (4) improving writing skills; (5) dealing with grammar and language difficulties; (6) seeking assistance and collaboration; (7) building confidence and motivation; (8) utilizing tools and strategies; (9) experiencing obstacles and distractions; and (10) giving recommendations.

Theme 1: Facing Writing Challenges

Students frequently encountered challenges related to mechanics, grammar, sentence structure, and organizing ideas, as well as managing time and dealing with low confidence. For example, one participant stated, "I'm not very good at writing in English because I struggle with how to construct what I'm trying to write properly" (Participant 3, Lines 24–26). Another shared, "I find it difficult, ma'am, to organize my writing. When it comes to ideas, it's easy, but organizing those ideas is really hard for me" (Participant 16, Lines 39–42). These struggles align with Sweller's Cognitive Load Theory (2020), which emphasizes the detrimental effects of excessive cognitive demands on working memory, particularly when juggling multiple writing tasks.

Research by Yuliawati (2021) further underscores the foundational role of grammar and vocabulary in writing quality, identifying insufficient mastery of these elements as a common barrier to effective writing. The participants' challenges with organizing ideas and maintaining coherence also reflect findings by Haryadi (2022), who noted that limited vocabulary and a lack of exposure to diverse writing formats exacerbate difficulties in constructing cohesive narratives. These observations suggest the need for targeted interventions to alleviate cognitive load and build foundational writing skills.

Theme 2: Seeking and Receiving Support and Feedback

Feedback emerged as a critical component of students' writing development, whether from teachers, peers, or digital tools. Participants valued the constructive nature of feedback, with one remarking, "It helped me evaluate my written works and pushed me to see how I could improve on my own" (Participant 6, Lines 66–68). Another noted, "Thanks to the teachers, ma'am, I'm slowly learning every day" (Participant 8, Line 38). The importance of feedback is supported by Shooshtari et al. (2023), who emphasize its role in fostering reflective and recursive writing practices.

Participants also highlighted the motivational impact of feedback, as seen in statements like, "Getting feedback boosts my confidence in writing in English" (Participant 11, Lines 104, 106). This aligns with Villaruz (2024), who underscores the dual function of feedback in correcting errors and building self-assurance. Additionally, the use of digital tools for immediate feedback mirrors findings by Wang (2023), who identified the efficacy of technology-mediated feedback in improving grammar and mechanics. Together, these insights underscore the importance of structured feedback mechanisms in enhancing students' writing proficiency.

Theme 3: Engaging in Writing Practice

Regular writing practice was a key driver of improvement for many participants. One participant shared, "I practice, ma'am. I read and write, so by writing, I can practice my grammar, and by reading, I can enhance my English skills" (Participant 13, Lines 34–35). Another added, "Sometimes I ask, but I rarely do, ma'am. Mostly, I search online and practice through tutorials" (Participant 16, Lines 46–48). The importance of consistent practice is well-documented in the literature, with Yundayani et al. (2020) noting that repeated writing tasks help internalize the processes of drafting, revising, and editing.

The diversity of writing tasks, such as essays and reflective narratives, was also highlighted by participants as instrumental in skill development. Choi and Cho (2020) support this, arguing that varied writing assignments promote the transfer of skills across contexts. The role of practice in fostering metacognitive awareness is further emphasized by Villaruz (2024), who identifies reflective writing as a pathway to improved grammar and organization.

Theme 4: Improving Writing Skills

Participants described incremental improvements in their writing through guided practice, structured instruction, and regular feedback. As one participant stated, "It helped me evaluate my writing and pushed me to improve on my own" (Participant 6, Lines 66–68).

Another noted, “Whenever I start an essay or a narrative paper, I strategize. I begin with my topic, preferably starting with an introduction, explain in the body, and conclude with a takeaway for the reader” (Group 1, Lines 162–166).

Research by Flower and Hayes (2004) supports these observations, emphasizing the role of cognitive strategies in planning, drafting, and revising writing.

The participants’ focus on reading as a means to expand vocabulary aligns with Mustadi and Amalia (2020), who highlight the symbiotic relationship between reading and writing proficiency. Together, these findings point to the importance of structured practice and strategic planning in developing effective writing skills.

Theme 5: Dealing with Grammar and Language Difficulties

Grammar and language use were among the most challenging aspects of writing for participants. One participant shared, “My problem is I’m having second thoughts about punctuation. I don’t know where to put the period or the comma” (Group 2, Lines 106–108). Another stated, “It’s the grammar, ma’am, and the structure, constructing sentences, ma’am” (Participant 8, Lines 28–29). These struggles reflect findings by Mart (2021), who identified grammar as both a cognitive framework and a practical skill requiring explicit instruction and contextual application.

Hakimi (2021) similarly emphasized the complexity of grammar, noting that difficulties often arise in transferring theoretical knowledge to practical writing tasks. The participants’ challenges with tense usage and sentence construction align with Rahmanadia’s (2021) observations on the cognitive load associated with managing grammatical structures in second-language writing.

Theme 6: Seeking Assistance and Collaboration

Collaboration played a significant role in students’ writing experiences, with many turning to peers, teachers, and family for support. One participant noted, “I ask teachers, ma’am, or watch YouTube videos to learn about things I don’t yet understand” (Group 1, Lines 140–141). Another shared, “I practice, ma’am, and then ask my classmates for help” (Participant 14, Line 32). This aligns with Chua and Bhar (2022), who highlight the benefits of peer feedback and collaborative learning environments in fostering writing development.

The participants’ reliance on collaborative strategies underscores the social dimensions of writing, as emphasized by constructivist theories. Villaruz (2024) further notes that cooperative learning fosters critical thinking and builds confidence, enabling students to approach writing with greater assurance.

Theme 7: Building Confidence and Motivation

Confidence and motivation were closely tied to positive reinforcement and visible progress. One participant remarked, “Thanks to the teachers, ma’am, I’m slowly learning every day” (Participant 8, Line 38). Another shared, “Through experience, I’ve learned a lot, ma’am” (Participant 10, Line 79). These observations align with Ryan and Deci’s (2000) Self-Determination Theory, which highlights the role of competence and relatedness in fostering intrinsic motivation.

Research by Shoostari et al. (2023) also supports the link between motivation and writing quality, noting that confidence grows through consistent practice and constructive feedback. Together, these findings underscore the importance of fostering a supportive environment to sustain student engagement in writing tasks.

Theme 8: Employing Tools and Strategies

Participants frequently relied on digital tools and personal strategies to enhance their writing. One shared, “Sometimes I use Google to search for the correct English” (Participant 9, Line 40), while another noted, “I ask teachers, ma’am, or watch YouTube videos to learn about things I don’t understand” (Group 1, Lines 140–141). These practices reflect findings by Wang (2023), who identified the effectiveness of digital tools in providing immediate feedback and supporting independent learning.

The integration of personal strategies, such as note-taking and outlining, also aligns with Martinez (2019), who emphasized the role of self-regulation in developing writing proficiency.

Theme 9: Experiencing Obstacles and Distractions

Distractions, both digital and environmental, were major impediments to productivity. One participant shared, “I can’t focus on writing because there are so many pending tasks” (Participant 3, Lines 46–48). Another noted, “While writing in the ICT lab, someone beside me kept asking questions, and I didn’t have the time to focus on what I was doing” (Group 1, Lines 63–64). These findings are consistent with Chang (2024), who identified digital distractions as a significant barrier to academic focus.

Theme 10: Giving Recommendations

Participants recommended reading more, minimizing distractions, practicing regularly, and seeking feedback. One shared, “By reading for comprehension, ma’am, and sometimes I use Google” (Participant 12, Line 44). These suggestions align with Halili and Diva (2023), who emphasize the role of reading in vocabulary acquisition and writing development. The focus on time management reflects Yang’s (2023) findings on the importance of structured writing routines for improving performance.

The Alignment of the Writing Proficiency Levels of Senior High Students and their Experiences

Table 2 shows an integration of quantitative and qualitative data, which demonstrates the importance of explanatory methods in mixed-methods research. Combining quantitative results with contextual narratives through the qualitative findings provides a comprehensive understanding of the factors contributing to students' writing challenges and highlights actionable pathways for instructional improvement.

Table 2. *Joint Display of the Alignment Between Quantitative and Qualitative Findings*

<i>Writing Proficiency Aspects</i>	<i>Quantitative Results</i>	<i>Qualitative Themes and Categories</i>	<i>Nature of Data Integration</i>
Content	Rating: 7.25/20 Grade: 69 Description: Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed	Theme: Facing Writing Challenges Categories: Struggling with idea generation, argument development, maintaining relevance	Explaining
Organization	Rating: 6.51/20 Grade: 68 Description: Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed	Theme: Facing Writing Challenges Categories: Struggling with logical sequencing, paragraph structure, and connecting ideas	Explaining
Vocabulary	Rating: 6.22/20 Grade: 67 Description: Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed	Theme: Improving Writing Skills Categories: Expanding vocabulary, learning new words, practicing usage in context	Explaining
Grammar and Language Use	Rating: 6.20/20 Grade: 67 Description: Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed	Theme: Dealing with Grammar and Language Difficulties Categories: Sentence structure, tense consistency, punctuation challenges	Explaining
Mechanics	Rating: 6.24/20 Grade: 67 Description: Did Not Meet Expectations / Failed	Theme: Facing Writing Challenges Categories: Struggling with spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and paragraphing	Explaining

The integration of quantitative and qualitative data in this study reveals that the nature of their alignment is fundamentally explanatory, as the qualitative findings elucidate the underlying reasons behind the quantitative results.

While the quantitative ratings for content, organization, vocabulary, grammar and language use, and mechanics show that TVL Senior High School students consistently failed to meet expectations across all aspects of writing proficiency, the qualitative themes provide rich, contextual insights into the specific struggles students face. This explanatory approach bridges numerical evaluations with students' lived experiences, offering a deeper understanding of their writing deficiencies and the systemic challenges that contribute to these outcomes.

The quantitative result for content (7.25/20; failed) highlights students' inability to generate and sustain ideas relevant to the topic. The qualitative findings expand this, emphasizing students' struggles with idea generation, argument development, and maintaining topic relevance. These challenges align with Cognitive Load Theory (Sweller, 1988), which suggests that writing requires balancing cognitive demands of content synthesis and organization. Studies by Macías and Dack (2023) indicate that students lacking exposure to structured writing tasks often face difficulty expanding and organizing ideas, reinforcing the need for instructional scaffolding.

The quantitative organization score (6.51/20; failed) indicates poor logical sequencing and paragraph structuring. Qualitative data explain that students face challenges in connecting ideas coherently and maintaining logical flow. Schema Theory (Rumelhart, 1980) supports this by highlighting that students without well-formed schemas for organizing ideas struggle with sequencing and cohesion. Behera (2023) further argues that teaching cohesive devices and outlining strategies can improve students' organizational skills, which is critical for addressing these deficiencies.

The vocabulary score (6.22/20; failed) reflects students' limited range and inappropriate word usage. Qualitative findings show that students recognize their need to expand their vocabulary through reading and contextual practice. According to Moon et al. (2019), limited vocabulary restricts students' ability to articulate complex ideas effectively. The qualitative data also point to gaps in idiomatic usage and precision, aligning with Nazzal et al. (2023), who emphasize the importance of integrating advanced vocabulary instruction into writing curricula.

The grammar and language use rating (6.20/20; failed) underscores students' struggles with sentence structure, tense consistency, and language devices. Qualitative data reveal these issues stem from a lack of foundational grammar knowledge and confidence in constructing complex sentences. Villaruz (2024) highlights that grammar proficiency is critical for clear communication but often requires explicit instruction and practice. This aligns with Rahman (2021), who stresses the role of targeted interventions to address students' difficulties with tense usage and sentence formation.

The mechanics rating (6.24/20; failed) shows consistent issues with spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and paragraphing. Qualitative data expand on this by identifying mechanical errors as major obstacles to clarity and professionalism in writing. Mustadi and Amalia (2020) argue that consistent practice of mechanics, combined with immediate feedback, is essential for mastering these foundational skills. Moreover, Kahraman and Kaya (2024) emphasize that mechanical inaccuracies detract from the quality of written work, supporting the need for focused instruction in this area.

Conclusions

The purpose of this study was to explore the writing proficiency of Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) Senior High School students, examining five critical aspects: content, organization, vocabulary, grammar and language use, and mechanics. By integrating quantitative scores and qualitative insights, the study aimed to uncover the challenges students face and provide a comprehensive understanding of their writing experiences. The findings reveal significant deficiencies across all dimensions of writing, highlighting the urgent need for targeted interventions to support student success.

TVL students struggle significantly with content development, as evidenced by their inability to create substantive and coherent arguments. The low scores for "Substantiveness" and "Thorough Development of Thesis" reflect challenges in critical thinking and deeper engagement with writing tasks. Similarly, poor organizational skills, such as logical sequencing and paragraph structuring, hinder students from effectively communicating their ideas. This underscores the need for explicit instruction in planning, outlining, and using cohesive devices to improve the flow of their writing.

Vocabulary proficiency remains a critical weakness. Limited word choice, poor contextual usage, and difficulty applying advanced vocabulary highlight the necessity of targeted vocabulary-building exercises. These deficiencies restrict students' ability to express ideas fluently and with sophistication, a challenge that is compounded by their struggles with grammar and language use. Errors in sentence construction, verb tense consistency, and grammatical precision suggest a pressing need for focused grammar instruction and practical application in authentic writing tasks.

Mechanics, encompassing spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and paragraphing, also present a major barrier. The inability to apply these conventions consistently undermines the clarity and professionalism of students' writing. Both quantitative and qualitative findings emphasize the importance of providing explicit instruction and repeated practice in writing mechanics to address these gaps.

Overall, the study demonstrates that TVL students face substantial hurdles in achieving writing proficiency. These challenges are not isolated but interconnected, reflecting a broader need for comprehensive, multifaceted instructional strategies. The findings highlight the importance of scaffolded writing support, metacognitive strategies, regular practice, and consistent feedback to address these deficiencies.

This research underscores the necessity of equipping TVL students with the skills needed to meet academic and professional demands. By addressing their struggles with content, organization, vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics, educators can help students develop confidence and competence in writing, ensuring their success in an increasingly communication-driven world.

Enhancing writing proficiency among Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) students requires a multifaceted approach that addresses content, organization, vocabulary, grammar, and mechanics. To improve content development, educators may implement scaffolded writing activities that break down complex tasks into manageable steps. Providing formative feedback focused on thesis clarity and idea expansion will help students refine their arguments and engage deeply with writing tasks. Teachers are recommended to lead these interventions, supported by school administrators in designing structured modules and providing resources.

To address organizational challenges, explicit instruction in outlining, paragraph structuring, and cohesive devices is essential. Teachers may incorporate peer review sessions and guided writing activities to help students learn to sequence ideas and maintain cohesion in their work logically. Such interventions will empower students to communicate their thoughts effectively in academic and professional settings, while curriculum designers should integrate these strategies into broader writing programs.

Vocabulary development is another critical area of focus. Teachers may integrate vocabulary exercises into classroom activities, offering contextual practice, peer collaboration, and the use of digital tools like vocabulary apps. This will enable students to expand their lexicon and use words effectively in context. Administrators should ensure access to resources that facilitate this learning, preparing students for future careers where communication is paramount.

Grammar instruction should be strengthened through focused lessons on sentence construction, tense consistency, and figures of speech. Corrective feedback and peer learning opportunities can help students internalize and apply grammar rules accurately. Schools may further support this effort by offering remedial sessions and grammar workshops to address persistent issues in students' writing.

Writing mechanics, including spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and paragraphing, must also be prioritized. Teachers may provide explicit instruction and repeated practice in these areas, complemented by the use of digital tools like Grammarly for real-time feedback. This approach will reinforce foundational skills and enable students to produce clearer and more professional writing. Administrators may facilitate this by ensuring access to digital tools and integrating mechanics-focused exercises into daily lessons.

Incorporating technology into writing instruction can greatly enhance students' learning experience. Digital tools provide immediate, personalized feedback, which complements traditional teacher and peer guidance. Teachers may integrate these tools into classroom activities, while administrators provide training to ensure their effective use. Combining technology with traditional feedback methods will accelerate students' progress in writing proficiency.

Metacognitive and time management strategies are equally important for helping students navigate the demands of writing tasks.

Reflective writing exercises and time management training can enhance students' planning and self-regulation skills, boosting their confidence and productivity. Teachers are recommended to lead workshops on these topics, with curriculum designers ensuring they are included in the broader educational framework.

Creating a collaborative learning environment through peer review sessions and group activities is another key recommendation. Peer interactions expose students to diverse perspectives, encouraging critical evaluation and mutual support. Teachers may facilitate these sessions, while schools provide conducive spaces and platforms for collaboration.

Writing instruction should also be tailored to align with the practical and vocational needs of TVL students. Designing writing tasks based on real-world scenarios will make the instruction more meaningful and applicable to their future careers. Teachers may lead this effort, with administrators ensuring access to industry-relevant resources and materials.

Finally, schools may promote a culture of writing excellence by organizing workshops, competitions, and establishing dedicated writing labs. These initiatives will foster continuous skill development and create an engaging environment that motivates students to improve their writing abilities. Administrators may spearhead these programs, ensuring they align with the overall goal of enhancing students' proficiency in written communication.

The findings of this study highlight a critical need for a comprehensive and targeted approach to improving writing proficiency among Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL) Senior High School students. Education should focus on addressing deficiencies across five key areas: content, organization, vocabulary, grammar and language use, and mechanics. These foundational aspects of writing are essential for both academic achievement and professional readiness in today's communication-driven world.

To strengthen content proficiency, educators should implement scaffolded writing tasks that guide students in generating ideas, constructing coherent arguments, and maintaining relevance to the topic. Explicit instruction on thesis formulation, critical thinking, and argumentation is crucial to help students produce well-developed and substantive writing. In addition, improving organizational skills should be a priority. Structured practices, such as outlining, paragraph organization, and the use of cohesive devices, should be emphasized. Incorporating metacognitive strategies, peer reviews, and guided writing sessions can further enhance logical sequencing and clarity in students' writing.

Vocabulary development requires advanced exercises that expand word choice, register, and contextual application. Technology-mediated tools can support this process by providing engaging and accessible platforms for practice while minimizing cognitive overload. Similarly, enhancing grammar and language use calls for focused instruction targeting sentence structure, tense consistency, and syntax. Integrating these lessons with writing tasks ensures students can apply grammatical knowledge effectively in real-world contexts.

Mastery of writing mechanics is another essential area of focus. Explicit teaching of spelling, punctuation, capitalization, and paragraphing, combined with regular practice and feedback, is vital for improving accuracy and professionalism in writing. Digital tools offering immediate feedback can be particularly effective in helping students refine these skills iteratively. Additionally, leveraging feedback from teachers, peers, and digital platforms is critical for growth. Constructive feedback fosters reflection, builds confidence, and encourages iterative improvement, enabling students to refine their writing over time.

Building confidence and motivation is equally important. A supportive learning environment that celebrates progress, provides positive reinforcement, and encourages perseverance can inspire students to engage more deeply with writing tasks. Addressing cognitive and environmental barriers, such as distractions and time management challenges, is also necessary. Structured writing schedules, stress-reduction techniques, and clear goal-setting can empower students to overcome these obstacles and maintain focus on their writing.

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